

D4.1 Pilot Plots Implementation

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Executive summary

The objective of the present deliverable is to describe (a) the different experimental parcels belonging to the three end-users involved in VITIGEOSS (Mastroberardino, Italy; Symington, Portugal; Torres, Spain) and (b) the experimental field activity that will be carried out to collect the data to be used for model calibration/training, fine-tuning and validation. The document will be structured as follows:

The first section will be dedicated to describing separately the three viticultural areas where the pilot plots will be located (Catalonia, Spain; Douro Region, Portugal; Irpinia, Italy), describing in details the locations (estates) where the selected vineyard parcels are situated.

The second section of the deliverable will provide a comprehensive description of the experimental designs that will be adopted to collect the data required to calibrate/train, fine-

tune and validate all the models included in VITIGEOSS. Thus, this section will include: (a) information about the location of the vineyards, the parcel characteristics like vineyard size, orientation, age, uniformity, cultivar and soil texture and depth and the common sugar and acidity thresholds used as harvest criteria; (b) a list of the measurements that will be carried out in the field and in the lab and will describe the protocols that will be adopted.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>EO</i>	<i>Earth Observation</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>a.s.l.</i>	<i>Above sea level</i>

Introduction

VITIGEOSS project aims at integrating an ecosystem of services that will be able to offer a range of information including forecasts, provisional models, advanced visualization, in a decision support system, able to support the winemakers in the vineyard management process. VITIGEOSS will move forward in the development of technology capabilities of systems such as satellite imagery, aerial images, and in-field sensors to integrate a set of Intelligent Services (IS), addressing specific aspects of the vineyard management, such as Weather/climate forecasting, Phenology, Diseases management, Crop management, and Sustainability and management.

The present deliverable addresses the description of the design of the pilot plots to be used to collect the data to calibrate/train, fine-tune and validate in the field all the models involved in VITIGEOSS. A full description of the selected vineyards and of experimental designs adopted for data collection in the field will be provided.

The prediction of plant phenological cycles in response to weather conditions is an important tool to help crops' management. Such tools provide useful information to improve, for instance, the timing of key agronomical practices like fertilization, pesticide application, irrigation and harvesting schedules. The most common approach to model plant phenology is based on the accumulation of Growing Degree Days (GDD), defined as the difference between the mean daily temperature and a set base temperature. Starting from January 1st, these models accumulate GDDs up to threshold values that trigger the passage from one phase to another. Another class of models belong to the Chilling and Forcing (CF) family, which extends the above approach also considering the dormancy phase, which is overcome with the accumulation of Chilling units, defining the beginning of the accumulation of GDDs [1]. As already observed by Fila et al. [1], there is a growing need to understand factors other than temperature influencing plant phenology to provide reliable predictions in changing climates. Here we will use an original solution which implements a very simplified carbon balance model, based on previous work by Carteni et al. [2]. Compared to traditional CF models, this approach considers the effects of air temperature, water availability and light on the main metabolic processes of the plant which drive the phenological cycle. The model simulation starts at the beginning of winter evaluating dormancy break as a function of air temperature, particularly cold temperatures for endodormancy break and warm temperatures for ecodormancy break leading to the reactivation of plant meristems and bud break. Each following phenological phase is assumed to proceed with a velocity proportional to the available photosynthates (function of air temperature, water availability and light). The succession of the different phases and consequent reallocation of resources is assumed to follow a hierarchical structure from bud break to fruit set. After fruit set, carbohydrates are allocated for sugar loading in the berries, leading to veraison and full maturation of the fruits. Available water is estimated using a simple bucket modelling approach [3] which provides a good compromise between accuracy and data requirements for its application [4].

For the phenology monitoring, LINKS will develop supervised machine learning models able to detect the occurrence of a phenological phase coupling several heterogeneous data, namely:

- Satellite data from Copernicus (Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and eventually Sentinel-3);
- In-situ data from weather stations;
- Pictures collected from in-field cameras installed in the fields;
- Pictures collected with drones.

The machine learning models will be trained using past phenological records and their accuracy will strongly depend on the availability of a wide ground truth dataset containing the achieved phenological phases, which shall be provided by the VITIGEOSS end-users (Mastroberardino, Symington, Torres), containing multiples years (from 2015 onward) and locations (all pilot plots

of VITIGEOSS). To cope with different conditions in terms of data availability, different models will be explored to achieve the same task, i.e. detecting the phenological phases.

Key crop parameters on biomass production, evapotranspiration and nitrogen will be monitored by eLEAF via satellite imagery. Crop parameters are produced on a weekly time step for the plots used in the pilot. The satellite data used to derive these variables is downloaded and pre-processed in order to correct satellite imagery to geometric and atmospheric conditions. Nitrogen content is derived from satellite reflectances using empirical functions derived by eLEAF. Satellite reflectances, land surface temperature, transmissivity and weather data are then combined in the ETLook model [5]. The ETLook models is an operational Surface Energy Balance Algorithm able to compute biomass production and evapotranspiration products based on satellite imagery. ETLook is used to generate detailed time series of among others biomass production, water consumption, stress and productivity and is used for field scale assessments up to continental monitoring. For example, ETLook is implemented in the FAO's WAPOR platform to provide access to satellite based data for monitoring and reporting on agriculture water productivity over Africa and the Near East [6]. Additionally, ETLook can separate the evapotranspiration into evapotranspiration (E) and transpiration (T). ETLook uses the energy balance to determine the available energy per pixel of 10 by 10 meters and determines how much energy is used for soil and air temperature changes. The residual energy is available for evapotranspiration process. Based on the amount of residual energy, ETLook calculates the crop evapotranspiration over natural vegetation or irrigated field. During this process the plant stress factors are calculated as well. When these stress factors are combined with other satellite derived parameters, it is possible to calculate the actual biomass production.

The disease and pest models have been used in the last years to help in the process to decrease their effects on yields and crops. For Downey mildew, several studies have modelled their infection lifecycle to better control its evolution. The monitoring of meteorological variables like precipitation, temperature and relative humidity have been used to predict the primary infections like the 3-10 rules (shoots at least 10 cm long, air temperature above 10 °C, 10 mm of continuous rain over a 24-48hr period) and the EPI model [7]. Along with strategies for modelling secondary infections thanks to the Goidanich table disease effects are usually under control [8]. Climate change seems to change the rules somewhat, but the commented techniques are still valid according to Fernández-González et al. [9]. Regarding Powdery Mildew, other mechanistic models have been created to manage its infection lifecycle like the PDE-ODE model [10] and machine learning models based on Bayesian networks [11]. The VITIGEOSS approach aims to benchmark those models using available data from the weather stations observations and take profit of forecasts from other services in the project (meteorological, weather, phenology) to adapt the current models to better plan the activities against these two diseases. The result will be a service able to predict the first infection and to define a seasonal risk level for better organization of the health keeping strategies, with the help of a recommendations about recipes for sprayer configurations, dosing intensities across fields, best dates for treatments, and a risk assessment picture at different time scales.

1. PILOT PLOT DESCRIPTION

Pilot plots will be located in three important European viticultural areas (Figure 1):

- Italy: Irpinia area
- Portugal: Douro Region
- Spain: Catalonia

Figure 1: Geographic location of the three end-ends where pilot plots will be conducted.

1.1 Pilot plots in Italy: the Mastroberardino’s estates

The terroir called Irpinia coincides with the province of Avellino. Irpinia is the cradle of Campania valuable wine productions with Denominations of Protected Origin (DOC/DOCG), recognizing the territory’s vocation, such as Taurasi made out of Aglianico, Fiano di Avellino made from the ancient Vitis Apiana, and Greco di Tufo. Viticulture in this area has ancient origins, dating back to the local population and then to the presence of Greek-Mycenaean settlers, who gave impetus to the age-old cultivation of the vine, then picked up by the Etruscans.

The Irpinia wine district is characterized by a high variability of soil and climatic conditions due to the presence of the Partenio and Terminio mountain ranges which cross the entire territory, and without any influence by the sea. This heterogeneity gives expression to a range of productive varieties, all based on the ancient native viticulture, which differ in relation to the soil, the planting density, the vines and the vegetative growth.

The climate is continental, with cold winters and rather cool summers, and characterized by extreme thermal excursions between day and night, features that give the wines, both red and whites, elegance, freshness and longevity.

The parcels that will be used for the VITIGE OSS activity in Italy will be located at five Mastroberardino estates (Mirabella Eclano, Montefusco, Montemarano, Pietradefusi, and Santa Paolina) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Geographic location of the five Mastroberardino's estates where pilot plots will be conducted.

1.1.1 Mirabella Eclano estate

The estate is located at Mirabella Eclano (Avellino, Italy; Latitude: 41° 3'41.94"N, Longitude: 14° 58'52.93"E) at an average altitude of 400 m a.s.l. It is the main estate owned by the Mastroberardino family, in the heart of the Taurasi DOCG area. The epicenter of the winery Aglianico production, research and experimentation. This estate is spread over several hills with different exposures and is dedicated to the production of red grapes, mainly Aglianico, on the slopes characterized by soils with a greater presence of organic matter and volcanic matrix, as well as white grape vines such as Fiano, Greco and Falanghina in areas where soils contain more limestone and clay. The estate covers 65 hectares with an altitude between 350 and 450 meters above sea level, producing some of the best winery *cru* such as Naturalis Historia Taurasi DOCG, Redimore Irpinia Aglianico DOC and Morabianca Irpinia Falanghina DOC. Weather conditions of the area are typical of a continental climate with cold and rainy winters and hot and dry summers. At this estate, the company has a Siap-Micros weather station that is in property, equipped with specific sensors of air temperature (minimum, maximum and average), relative humidity (minimum, maximum and average), rainfall, leaf wetness, wind speed and direction, and global solar radiation.

In the last decade, annual rainfall was on average 833 mm (50% occurring in the period between November and March). Total rainfall during July and August was on average 73 mm. The best wine vintages generally occur in the years when rainfall is relatively low during berry ripening (between August and September). In the last 20 years, the best vintages for the Taurasi wines occurred in 1997, 2004, 2007, 2008 (these years were characterized by a total rainfall from August to October of 54, 52, 41, 71 mm, respectively).

1.1.2 Montefusco estate

Situated in the north-east of the Greco di Tufo DOCG area, this estate represents a cornerstone of the work of viticultural zoning about the denomination started in the eighties. Here the Mastroberardino family produces the *cru* Novaserra Greco di Tufo DOCG. The vineyards on the hills of Montefusco are located in an airy basin that receives light from dawn to dusk, with a good protection from the phenomena of fog and stagnant moisture. The highest dwelling of the plants of the denomination can be found here, at around 550 meters, under conditions allowing relevant thermal excursions, especially in the months of August, September, and October, making it possible for a slow and peculiar evolution of the maturation of the grapes. The estates covers around 5 hectares.

At this estate, the company has a Siap-Micros weather station that is in property, equipped with specific sensors of air temperature (minimum, maximum and average), relative humidity (minimum, maximum and average), rainfall, and leaf wetness.

1.1.3 Montemarano estate

At about 20 kilometers from the winery, Montemarano represents a historic site in the Taurasi wine production, in the most southern part of the DOCG area. The estate now plays an important role in the cultivation of Aglianico grapes for the production of Taurasi Riserva DOCG. The estate is composed by two different blocks with a total surface of 10 hectares. Here the proximity of the Picentini mountains and the continental climate creates the conditions for a foothill viticulture of great value. In this area, extreme thermal excursions and the slower maturation provide the conditions for a late harvest, usually in November, offering grapes richer in tannins and acidity, enhancing the character of longevity. For these reasons, Montemarano is the site for the production of the Taurasi Riserva wine that is able to best express these organoleptic prerogatives.

At this estate, the company has a Siap-Micros weather station that is in property of Campania Region, equipped with specific sensors of air temperature (minimum, maximum and average), relative humidity (minimum, maximum and average), rainfall, and leaf wetness.

In the highest part of the estate, nearly 620 meters above sea level, the unique climatic conditions allow for the process of drying grapes on the vine. Thanks to a research program developed in the winery, a dessert wine from Aglianico grapes with the development of noble rot was born, part of the Irpinia DOC denomination, which represents a new frontier of knowledge for the territory. This wine has made possible to discover and develop sensory profiles of this variety that were previously unexplored.

1.1.4 Pietradefusi estate

Pietradefusi is one of the oldest villages in the province of Avellino, mentioned by the latin Tito Livio. The estate, located to the North of the town, is characterized by a soil rich in minerals, which makes the fruit particularly aromatically expressive. The grapes, due to the peculiarities of their position, the nature of the soil and sun exposure, are intended for experiments of considerable interest for the further development of the potential of *Aglianico*. The *Lacrimarosa Irpinia Rosato DOC* produced here represents further proof of the versatility of *Aglianico* and the personality of its chosen land, Irpinia. Management of the vineyards is specifically aimed towards obtaining a rose' wine with freshness, delicacy and aroma. Mild leaf removal, as usually made on white grapes, is carried out throughout the vineyards in order to not expose the grapes to the sun. A very contained cluster thinning, and all other managerial

tasks are aimed towards achieving vegetative vigour of the foliage, late growth arrest, and grapes with characteristics closer to white varieties.

1.1.5 Santa Paolina estate

Santa Paolina and Tufo are the main villages in the production area of Greco di Tufo DOCG. The Greco grapes from this estate are intended for the production of the *cru* selection Vignadangelo Greco di Tufo DOCG, structured and elegant, supported by a good acidity. In the history of Greco, a variety that would have disappeared without the patient recovery made by Mastroberardino family after the war, the Vignadangelo selection is the result of extensive research of nature and position of the terrain to allow for the best expression of the variety. The altitude of the Irpinian hills (350-650 m a.s.l.), the particular microclimate, with thermal excursions between day and night, as much as 20 °C, make this small part of terroir unique in Italian viticulture panorama. Despite its small size, the three most important DOCG of the Campania region are concentrated here: Taurasi, Fiano di Avellino, Greco di Tufo.

1.2 Pilot plots in Portugal: the Symington’s estates

The Douro Region is the largest area of mountain vineyard in the world, with around 100 km from west to east and with vineyards from 90 meters up to 600 meters on the hillsides. The region and is protected from the Atlantic maritime climate by the mighty 1,400-meter-high Serras do Marão and Montemuro to the west and the valley is primarily composed of the specific schistous soils, that characterize the region.

For this project were selected different plots of Touriga Nacional and Touriga Franca in two different locations, one at sub-region Cima Corgo - Quinta do Bomfim - and another one at Douro Superior - Quinta do Ataíde (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Geographic location of the two Symington’s estates where pilot plots will be conducted.

1.2.1 Quinta do Ataíde

The Ataíde estate is situated at Vilaríça Valley (41°14'36''N, 7° 06'55''W), in the northern extremity of the Douro Superior. Within 83 hectares of organic vineyards, and between 138- and 172-meters elevation above sea level.

The average annual rainfall is 536 mm, and the “Growing Season Average Temperature” (April to October) is 20.8 °C, which is comparable with other of the Douro’s best regions, but colder winters and hotter summers are an integral part of this annual average and combine to create unique conditions for the development of the vines and their fruits.

With high summer temperatures and virtually no rainfall in July and August, dry farming of the Ataíde vineyard would be virtually impossible, but a carefully controlled use of drip irrigation guarantees a protection of the vines from excessive hydric stress and prevents dehydration.

1.2.2 Quinta do Bomfim

Quinta do Bomfim is located at the heart of the Douro Valley (41°11'19''N, 7° 32'20''W), at Pinhão. The estate has near 75 hectares of vineyards, spread all over the hill, with altitude variation from 90 to 350 meters above sea level and exhibition predominantly to south. Contrarily to Ataíde, at Bomfim there is not irrigation and the vineyard management is done following the integrated protection guidelines.

The temperature during the “Growing Season” is 20.7 °C and the annual rainfall is 658 mm, mainly distributed from October to May. During the summer the temperatures are high and precipitation scarce. The soils are the derived from schists bedrock silt loam with 1.2 m deep and an average of 40% gravel elements, low in organic matter (1.0-1.2%) with a pH acidic.

This estate contributes with some of the best grapes for the production of exquisite port wines.

1.3 Pilot plots in Spain: the Torres’ estates

The two Torres’ estates involved in VITIGE OSS activities are located in two major viticultural areas in Catalonia: Penedès and Costers del Segre (Figure 4).

The Penedès region is wide and open, covering a long strip of land between the sea and the mountains, half-way between Barcelona and Tarragona. The Denomination of Origin is made up of three distinct zones: The Penedès Superior (near the inland mountain range), The Penedès Marítim (between the sea and the coastal hills) and the plain between these areas, known as the Penedès Central. The Penedès enjoys a wide variety of micro-climates, marked by the different altitudes and the proximity of the sea. The climate is typically Mediterranean, mild and warm. The diversity of the DO Penedès’ wines is based on the singularity of the region. A thousand tastes, aromas, bodies and structures are the result of these differences in climate, territory and the variety of the soils that make up the region, marked by the green of the hills and valleys or the blue of the Mediterranean.

The area of Costers del Segre Designation is different, with inverted geological and climatic characteristics. The connecting link is the middle basin of the river Segre, between the Pyrenees and the Ebro, and the dry climate of the interior, away from the influence of the sea and marked by an elevated insolation, a scant rainfall and persistent fogs of winter moisture. The vineyards are located between 200 and 1100 m of altitude. The soil is calcareous sand covered, with a great uniformity in all the denomination. The subzones of Artesa and Pallars are the northernmost, with vines of greater altitude and Pyrenean influence. Raimat, to the

far East, has a mild relief and continental climate. The subzone of the Segrià, Lleida plane, is characteristic of non-irrigated land. The Garrigues and the Riucorb valleys are arid lands.

Figure 4: Geographic location of the two Torre’s estates where pilot plots will be conducted.

1.3.1 Aranyó

Aranyó estate, situated in the area of Juneda, in the heart of the Les Garrigues region, is a real Mediterranean sanctuary of olive trees more than four hundred years old. At the end of the nineties Torres began to grow vines here in a typically continental climate some 450 m in altitude. Since 2012 the wine "Purgatori" is produced here. The estate has more than 200 hectares of vineyards, with altitude variation from 300 to 550 meters above sea level.

The average temperature during the “Growing Season” is 19.6 °C and the annual rainfall is 353 mm. During the summer the temperatures are high (above 35 °C) and precipitation scarce. In winter, temperatures below 0 °C are usual in this area. The soils are, in general, shallow, and normally limited by layers of calcium carbonate. They are very basic soils (high pH) and medium, silty textures. These characteristics, together with a dry climate in summer, with scant precipitation and high-water demand, create a potential situation of significant water stress in the warm season.

1.3.2 Sant Martí Sarroca

The estate has 14 hectares at 300 metres in altitude, and it is presided by a large, fortified farm, which is home to an unusual collection of almost 300 stocks where you can observe the most legendary and diverse varieties in the world.

The average temperature during the “Growing Season” is 19 °C and the annual rainfall is 536 mm. In this estate, it is located the plot where part of the studies of the VITIGE OSS project will be carried out. The soils are deep, well drained and of fine texture, with few coarse elements. On the surface, moderately stony, with gravel frequent and dark yellowish brown in colour. These soils have low organic matter content, very high calcium carbonate content and the reaction is slightly alkaline.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGNS OF THE FIELD TRIALS

The pilot plots will be used to collect the full dataset required to calibrate/train, fine-tune and validate the following five models: vine phenology prediction, vine phenology monitoring, disease risk management, and key crop indicator model. Taking into account the requirements of each of the model, specific parcels were selected for each of them.

2.1 Vine phenology prediction and monitoring

All the field experimental activities of this task will aim to collect the data needed for the calibration/training, fine-tuning and validation of both the phenology prediction model and the phenology monitoring model. Therefore, they will include also the parcels where the in-field cameras will be installed and drone flights will be carried out.

2.1.1 Selected parcels

The models will be calibrated/validated on the following five grapevine cultivars; Aglianico and Greco (Mastroberardino); Touriga Franca and Touriga Nacional (Symington); Syrah (Torres).

2.1.1.1 Parcels of Aglianico

For Aglianico, a total of five parcels located at three Mastroberardino's estates will be selected and used to track phenology. Two of these parcels will be located at Mirabella Eclano, two of them at Montemarano, and the one at Pietradefusi.

2.1.1.1.1 Aglianico at Mirabella Eclano

At Mirabella Eclano, two parcels of Aglianico will be used for this part of the project. The first parcel is a vineyard of about 1 hectare and located at an altitude of 400 m a.s.l (Avellino, Italy; Latitude: 41°03'04"N, 14°58'52"E) with a slope of 10% facing North (Figure 5). The vines, planted in 2004 in a North-South row orientation, are Aglianico grapevines grafted onto K5BB rootstocks, trained to a bilateral spur cordon (with 8 spurs/vine), and spaced 1.0 × 2.5 m (corresponding to a planting density of 4000 vines/ha). The permanent cordon is located at 80 cm above the soil. The soil is deep with sandy loam texture, volcanic and clay presence in its depths and limestone throughout the profile, well drained.

Figure 5: View of the first Aglianico parcel at Mirabella Eclano estate.

The second parcel is a vineyard is about 0.8 hectares and located at an altitude of about 360 m a.s.l. with a slope of 17 % facing West (Figure 6). The vines, planted in 1975 in an East-West row orientation, are old Aglianico grapevines grafted onto not available rootstock, trained to a bilateral spur cordon, and spaced 2.0×3.0 m (corresponding to a planting density of 1.660 vines/ha). The permanent cordon is located at 100 cm above the soil. The soil is deep with sandy loam texture, volcanic and clay presence in its depths.

Figure 6: View of the second Aglianico parcel at Mirabella Eclano estate.

2.1.1.1.2 Aglianico at Montemarano

At Montemarano, three parcels of Aglianico will be used for this part of the project. The first two parcels are vineyards of about 0.5 hectares each and located at an altitude of 610 m a.s.l. with different slopes of average 14% facing North (Figure 7). The vines, planted in 2004 in different row orientations, are Aglianico grapevines grafted onto K5BB rootstocks, trained to a bilateral spur cordon (with 8 spurs/vine), and spaced 1.0×2.5 m (corresponding to a planting density of 4000 vines/ha). The permanent cordon is located at 80 cm above the soil. The soil is mainly clay with good organic matter content and crushed limestone.

Figure 7: View of two of the Aglianico parcel at Montemarano estate.

The second parcel is a vineyard of 3.6 hectares and located at an altitude of 540 m a.s.l. with different slopes of average 18% mainly facing South (Figure 8). The vines, planted in 2001 in different row orientations, are Aglianico grapevines grafted onto SO4 rootstocks, trained to a bilateral spur cordon (with 10 spurs/vine), and spaced 1.5×2.8 m (corresponding to a planting density of 2,380 vines/ha). The permanent cordon is located at 90 cm above the soil. The soil is mainly clay with good organic matter content and crushed limestone.

Figure 8: View of the second Aglianico parcel at Montemarano estate.

2.1.1.1.3 Aglianico at Pietradefusi

The vineyard is about 2.3 hectares and located at an altitude of 320 m a.s.l with a slope of 23% facing West-North (Figure 9). The vines, planted in 2001 in near North-South row orientation, are Aglianico grapevines grafted onto SO4 rootstocks, trained to a bilateral spur cordon (with 10 spurs/vine), and spaced 1.5×2.8 m (corresponding to a planting density of 2,380 vines/ha). The permanent cordon is located at 90 cm above the soil. The soil is mainly clay, rich in minerals, with good organic matter content.

Figure 9: View of the Aglianico parcel at Pietradefusi estate.

2.1.1.2 Parcels of Greco

For the cultivar Greco, a total of four parcels located at three Mastroberardino’s estates (Mirabella Eclano, Montefusco, and Santa Paolina) will be selected and used to track phenology.

2.1.1.2.1 Greco at Mirabella Eclano

Two Greco parcels will be located at this site (Figure 10). The vineyards are about 1.0 and 0.6 hectares, respectively, and have different row orientation. They are located at an altitude of about 320 m a.s.l. with a slope of 23% in the bigger block facing West-South . The vines, planted in 2002 are Greco grapevines grafted onto 1103P and SO4 rootstocks, trained to a single Guyot (with an average of 10 buds/vine), and spaced 1.0 × 2.5 m (corresponding to a planting density of 4,000 vines/ha). The cane is located at 80 cm above the soil. The soil is deep with sandy loam texture, volcanic and clay presence in its depths and limestone throughout the profile, well drained.

Figure 10: View of the Greco parcels at Mirabella Eclano estate.

2.1.1.2.2 Greco at Montefusco

The vineyard is about 2.6 hectares and located at an altitude of 470 m a.s.l. with a slope of 15% facing South (Figure 11). The vines, planted in 2004 in different row orientations, mainly North-South, are Greco grapevines grafted onto 420A rootstocks, trained to a bilateral guyot (with about 16 buds/vine), and spaced 1.0 × 2.5 m (corresponding to a planting density of 4,000 vines/ha). The cane is located at 80 cm above the soil. The soil is mainly clay deriving from the parent rock of sandstone and marly limestone.

Figure 11: View of the Greco parcel at Montefusco estate.

2.1.1.2.3 Greco at Santa Paolina

The vineyard is about 3.8 hectares and located at an altitude of 320 m a.s.l. with a slope of 18% facing East (Figure 12). The vines, planted in 1999 in West-East row orientation, are Greco grapevines grafted onto SO4 and 1103P rootstocks, trained to a bilateral guyot (with about 16 buds/vine), and spaced 1.5 × 2.8 m (corresponding to a planting density of 2,380 vines/ha). The cane is located at 90 cm above the soil. The soil is mainly clay, good in limestone.

Figure 12: View of the Greco parcel at Santa Paolina estate.

2.1.1.3 Parcels of Syrah

For the cultivar Syrah, four parcels located at two Torres' estates will be selected and used to track phenology. Three of these parcels are located at Aranyó (that will be used to compare vines with three training systems) and the one at Sant Martí Sarroca.

2.1.1.3.1 Syrah at Aranyó

The selected plot is a 2.7 ha Syrah vineyard located at Juneda, Lleida, Spain (41.486889, 0.823780) (Figure 13). The rootstock is 1103P. Vines were planted in 2008 at a spacing of 2.2 m x 1.0 m with W-E row orientation. In the plot there are three different training systems. Some vines are cordon-trained to a vertical shoot position, some are cordon-trained but not to a vertical position (shading grapes) and another group is cordon-trained where the vegetation that faces the afternoon sunlight is not trimmed to avoid sunburns. The plot is 363 m a.s.l. and has a 2% slope. The vines are drip irrigated using drippers spaced 1 m apart along a single drip line per vine row. Three different irrigation strategies are used as identified in the figure.

Figure 13: View of the Syrah plot at Aranyó estate.

2.1.1.3.2 Syrah at Sant Martí Sarroca

The Syrah parcel selected for this part of the project is located in the Colecció Mas Rabell plot, a Grape Collection vineyard located at Sant Martí Sarroca, Barcelona, Spain (41.374548, 1.629578) (Figure 14). Fifteen Syrah vines were planted in 2005 at a spacing of 2.2 m x 1.0 m with W-E row orientation. The rootstock is R110. They are cordon-trained to a vertical shoot position. The plot is 256 m a.s.l. and has a 2.3% slope. The vines are drip irrigated using drippers.

Figure 14: View of the Syrah plot at Sant Martí Sarroca estate.

2.1.1.4 Parcels of Touriga Franca

For the cultivar Touriga Franca, a total of four parcels located at two Symington's estates (Quinta do Ataíde and Quinta do Bomfim) will be selected and used to track phenology.

2.1.1.4.1 Touriga Franca at Quinta do Ataíde

At Quinta do Ataíde, two Touriga Franca parcels will be used for this part of the project. The first selected Touriga Franca vineyard (41° 15'03''N, 7° 06'34''W) was planted in 2013, grafted in 196-17 Cl rootstock (Figure 15). This parcel is 2.02 hectares and is located at an altitude of 160 meters above sea level. The plants are oriented southeast to northwest, spaced 2.2 m between rows, 1.0 along the row, the vines are trained on a vertical trellis, pruned on unilateral Royat cordon, with around 10 buds per vine. The soil derived from schist is a sandy loam with 1.5 m deep and an average of 45% gravel elements, low in organic matter (1.0%) with a pH near to neutral.

Figure 15: View of the Touriga Franca plot at Quinta do Ataíde estate.

The second selected parcel of Touriga Franca is included in the Symington’s Grape Library, an experimental vineyard planted in 2014 at Quinta do Ataíde with the aim of studying the adaptability of different varieties to specific climate conditions (Figure 16). In this vineyard there are 53 *Vitis vinifera* varieties, comprising indigenous Douro, Portuguese varieties and 5 foreign varieties, used as benchmarks. Each variety is represented with 200 plants, installed in two contiguous vineyard parcels, covering 2.25 hectares.

The vineyard is grafted in 196-17 rootstock, the plants are oriented in west/southwest to east/northeast, spaced at 2.2 m between rows, 1.0 m along the row and trained on a vertical trellis, uniformly pruned on a unilateral Royat cordon, with approximately 10 buds per vine.

The Symington research team is recording phenology data here, for all varieties in the major stages, following a strict observation protocol. In addition, during maturation, samples are collected every week, with the aim of studying the sugar accumulation process in different cultivars.

Figure 16: View of the Symington’s Grape Library at Quinta do Ataíde estate.

2.1.1.4.2 Touriga Franca at Quinta do Bomfim

At Quinta do Bomfim, two Touriga Franca parcels will be used for this part of the project. The first selected Touriga Franca vineyard (42° 11' 38'' N 7° 32' 05'' W) was planted in 2016, grafted in 196-17 Cl rootstock (Figure 17). The parcel is 2.33 hectares and is located at an altitude of approximately 220 meters a.s.l.. The plants are oriented in west southwest to east/ northeast, narrow terraces with one line, spaced at 3.5 m between rows (horizontal projection), 0.9 m along the row and trained on a vertical trellis, pruned on a unilateral Royat cordon, with approximately 8 buds per vine.

Figure 17: View of the Touriga Franca plot at Quinta do Bomfim estate.

The second selected parcel of Touriga Franca is included in a Grape Library vineyard planted in 2015 at Quinta do Bomfim, with the remaining plants from Ataíde (Figure 18). In this field are represented 29 varieties, only Portuguese cultivars and mainly from Douro. This experimental field has the particularity of combining in the same plot two types of vineyard: part of the vines is in vertical rows and other part in narrow terraces. Also, in this parcel, phenology and maturation are controlled, following the same protocol like Ataíde.

The vineyard is grafted in 196-17 rootstock, spaced 1.0 m along the row, in vertical rows the distance between rows is 2.0 m and in the narrow terraces 2.7 m. The plants are trained on a vertical trellis, uniformly pruned on a unilateral Royat cordon, with around 10 buds per vine.

Figure 18: View of the Symington’s Grape Library at Quinta do Bomfim estate.

2.1.1.5 Parcels of Touriga Nacional

For the cultivar Touriga Nacional, a total of four parcels located at two Symington’s estates (Quinta do Ataíde and Quinta do Bomfim) will be selected and used to track phenology.

2.1.1.5.1 Touriga Nacional at Quinta do Ataíde

At Quinta do Ataíde, two Touriga Nacional parcels will be used for this part of the project. The first selected Touriga Nacional vineyard ($41^{\circ}14'38''N$, $7^{\circ}06'54''W$) used in this study was planted in 2014, grafted in 196-17 Cl rootstock (Figure 19). The parcel is 2.1 hectares and is located at an elevation of approximately 140 m a.s.l. The plants are oriented in west/southwest to east/ northeast, spaced at 2.2 m between rows, 1.0 m along the row and trained on a vertical trellis, uniformly pruned on a unilateral Royat cordon, with approximately 10 buds per vine. The soil, derived from schist is a silty loam with 1.5 m deep and an average of 50% gravel elements, low to very low in organic matter (0.8-1.0%) with a pH from acidity to neutral.

Figure 19: View of the Touriga Nacional plot at Quinta do Ataíde estate.

The second selected parcel of Touriga Franca at Quinta do Ataíde is included in the Symington’s Grape Library, that was already described previously (Figure 16).

2.1.1.5.2 *Touriga Nacional at Quinta do Bomfim*

At Quinta do Bomfim, two Touriga Nacional parcels will be used for this part of the project. The first selected Touriga Nacional vineyard (41° 11’28’’N, 7° 32’05W) was planted in 2015, grafted in 196-17 Cl rootstock (Figure 20). The parcel is 0.31 hectares and is located at an elevation of approximately 150 m a.s.l. The plants are oriented north-south, spaced at 2.2 m between rows, 1.0 m along the row and trained on a vertical trellis, uniformly pruned on a unilateral Royat cordon, with approximately 8 buds per vine.

Figure 20: View of the Touriga Nacional plot at Quinta do Bomfim estate.

The second selected parcel of Touriga Nacional at Quinta do Bomfim is included in the Grape Library, that was already described previously (Figure 18).

2.1.2 Experimental design for data collection for the phenology models

In each selected parcel, all the measurements required to calibrate/train/validate the phenology models will be carried out on four groups (blocks) of 10 vines each (a total of 40 vines). An example of the experimental design is reported in Figure 21. At three of the selected parcels per end-user, one in-field camera within one the four blocks (block 3 in case of the experimental design reported in Figure 20). The cameras will point the vines used for tracking vine phenology.

Figure 21: Schema of experimental design used for the phenology measurements in the field. Each circle represents one vine; the star indicates the location where the in-field camera will be installed.

The cameras will be installed in the following parcels:

- Mastroberardino: two Aglianico parcels (located at Mirabella Eclano and Montemarano estate, respectively; Figures 5 and 7) and one Greco parcel (at Mirabella Eclano estate; Figure 10).
- Symington: two Touriga Nacional parcels (located at Quinta do Ataíde and Quinta do Bomfim; Figures 19 and 20) and one Touriga Franca Parcel (located at Quinta do Ataíde; Figure 15).
- Torres: three Syrah parcels (located at the Aranyó estate; Figure 13). The three parcels differ among them for the training system adopted (cordons trained to a vertical shoot position; cordons not trained to a vertical position; and cordons with asymmetric summer shoot pruning).

The installed in-field camera should have the following technical characteristics:

- Optical sensor + IR with a full HD resolution of the optical sensor;
- Water and dust proof (IP66);
- To be mounted on a pole to avoid spay (height 3-4m);
 - Alternative solution would be camera with auto cleaning features (very costly), manual spraying in the surrounding of cameras, periodic manual cleaning of cameras;
- Self-powered through a solar panel plus battery;
- Connectivity: cellular (3G/4G) connectivity and Wi-Fi (nice to have);
- Pan Tilt and Zoom (PTZ) capabilities;
- Data collection requirements: data (images) shall be automatically sent to a remote server (e.g. FTP, HTTP) without requiring additional costs for third-party systems
- Programmability: it should be possible to remotely define the periodicity of picture and the PTZ setting

The in-field cameras, the high-level schema of which is shown in Figure 22, could be installed using a new pole with a new plinth, or attached to an existing pole with plinth. Also, the connectivity and the logger could be provided by the camera, or by a separate

modem and component. In the latter case, all the additional hardware should be allocated in the cabinet.
 The exact camera specifications will be known once a final supplier will be identified.

Figure 22: High-level schemas of the in-field cameras that will be installed at the end-users pilot plots. Two Solutions are shown: (left) requiring a new plinth, (right) attached to an existing pole with an existing plinth

2.1.3 Measurements

2.1.3.1 Phenology measurements

The phenology measurements will be carried out in three vegetative seasons in all the selected parcels. This experimental activity will collect a dataset suitable for the calibration/training, fine-tuning and validation of both phenology models (prediction and monitoring models). The annual cycle of the grapevines will be analysed detecting the day of the year (DOY) when the following six phenological stages occur: bud break, blooming, fruit set, veraison, berry maturity, and leaf fall. The scale described by Baggiolini [12] will be used as a reference for phenology detection. In detail, the Baggiolini’s phases adopted as a reference for bud break, blooming, fruit set and veraison will be stages C (Green tip), I (open flower), J (fruit set), and M (berry color change), respectively (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Reference phenological stages as indicated by the Baggiolini scale [12].

These phenological stages will be assumed to be achieved when 50-60% of the observed plant organ will be at the reference phenological stage (90% of the berries in case of veraison; hereafter nearly full veraison stage).

The grape maturity stage will be considered as achieved when berry composition will reach the cultivar-specific composition targets defined by the three end-users (Table 1).

Table 1: Berry composition at grape maturity stage for the five cultivars involved in VITIGE OSS

Cultivar	End-user	Total soluble solids (°Brix)	Total acidity (g/L tartaric acid)
Aglianico	Mastroberardino	23.5	7.0
Greco	Mastroberardino	22.0	8.5
Syrah	Torres	24.0	5.5
Touriga Franca	Symington	22.0	4.7
Touriga Nacional	Symington	23.0	5.0

The leaf fall stage indicates the end of the vegetative season of the vines and will be assumed to be reached when 50% of leaves are fallen. The evaluation will be done visually in the field with the help of references images (Figure 24).

The frequency of phenology measurements will vary depending on the period of the year. In detail, the following three measurement frequency will be adopted: (a) biweekly in the periods when the target stages are distant in time (for instance right after fruit set is achieved), (b) weekly at the onset of the target stages, and (c) every 3-5 days when the target stages are approaching. For bud break, blooming, fruit set, and leaf fall, this will occur when 10% (50% for veraison) of the observed organs have reached the target phenological stage. In the case of the grape maturity stage, measurements will be taken every 3-5 days starting when soluble solids content have reached 80% of the target values (reported in Table 2). The specific day of the year when each phenological stage occurred will be estimated by interpolation.

Stage	Image
20% leaf fall	
50% leaf fall	
80% leaf fall	

Figure 24: Reference images to define the percentage of leaf fall.

2.1.3.2 Irrigation water applied and vine physiology measurements

The phenology prediction model developed by UNINA is a process-based model that simulates carbon partitioning among vine organs. For this reason, it simulates also leaf area growth and requires, as an input water applied with irrigation. In each selected parcel, leaf area index will be estimated at the end of July (when in the areas where these trials will be carried out most of the vegetative growth is already over). This will be done estimating vine total leaf area using non-destructive methods [13]. Data applied with irrigation will be measured and provided weekly. Vine water status (leaf water potential) will be measured at least once per month throughout the vegetative season.

2.1.3.3 Image collection with the in-field cameras and drones

The images from in-field cameras shall be sent to a remote server, either via the FTP or the HTTP protocol. In case of FTP, a specific adapter will be created to periodically check the presence of new images, retrieve them, store them in a separate file repository and trigger their analysis by calling the module that will contain the phenological phase detection model. In case the images will be uploaded via HTTP on a third-party system, such system should make

them available via HTTP APIs. In this case the adapter will periodically check the availability of new images using the available APIs. With respect to drones, the requirement is that they should be capable to produce an ortorectified map (geoTIFF) with a resolution below 1 m and cover the pilot plot size. The number of flights will depend on the available budget and on the cost of each flight. In order to save money and be effective, the flight shall be scheduled when it is predicted that a phenological phase will occur so as to study the spatial variability within the pilot plots. Images from drones will be manually sent by the supplier and manually uploaded on a data repository. An adapter will be developed to take the images from the data repository.

2.2 Disease risk management

Specific field trials will be carried out to collect all the data required to train and validate the disease risk management model.

2.2.1 Selected parcels

The field trials will be carried out on a total of three plots (one per end-user). Two of these trials will be specifically designed to both train and validate the disease risk management model (one plot of Greco at Mastroberardino's and one plot of Touriga Nacional at Symington's). Furthermore, to additionally test the replicability of the results, the disease risk management model will be also validated on an additional cultivar grown in a different area (one plot of Syrah at Torres').

2.2.1.1 Parcel of Greco at Montefusco (Mastroberardino)

The vineyard is around 1.5 ha and located at an altitude of 490 m a.s.l. with a slope of 15% facing South (Figure 25: View of the Greco plot at Montefusco estate selected for the disease risk management model.). The vines, planted in 2004 in mainly North-South, are Greco grapevines grafted onto 420A rootstocks, trained to a bilateral guyot (with about 16 buds/vine), and spaced 1.0 × 2.5 m (corresponding to a planting density of 4,000 vines/ha). The cane is located at 80 cm above the soil. The soil is mainly clay deriving from the parent rock of sandstone and marly limestone.

Figure 25: View of the Greco plot at Montefusco estate selected for the disease risk management model.

2.2.1.2 Parcel of Touriga Nacional at Quinta do Bomfim (Symington)

The Touriga Nacional parcel (41° 11'28''N 7° 32'15W) used for the model diseases calibration was planted in 2015, grafted in 196-17 Cl rootstock (Figure 26). The parcel is 0.45 hectares and is located at an elevation of approximately 150 m a.s.l. The plants are oriented north-south, spaced at 2.2 m between rows, 1.0 m along the row and trained on a vertical trellis, uniformly pruned on a unilateral Royat cordon, with approximately 8 buds per vine.

Figure 26: View of the Touriga Nacional plot at Quinta do Bomfim estate selected for the disease risk management model.

2.2.1.3 Parcel of Syrah at Aranyó (Torres)

The vineyard is a 0.6 ha Syrah vineyard located at Juneda, Lleida, Spain (41.486143, 0.825010) (Figure 27). The rootstock is 1103P. Vines were planted in 2008 at a spacing of 2.2 m x 1 m with SW-NE row orientation. They are cordon-trained to a vertical shoot position. The plot is 365 m a.s.l. and has a 2% slope. The vines are drip irrigated using drippers spaced 1 m apart along a single drip line per vine row.

Figure 27: View of the Syrah plot at Aranyó estate selected for the disease risk management model.

2.2.2 Experimental design for data collection for the disease risk management model

The experimental design adopted for the Greco (Mastroberardino) and Touriga Nacional parcels will include three treatments and four replicates (block). Within each block, the five central vines (to avoid mixed effects that can occur in the borders vines) will be used to carry out the measurements (a total of 60 vines = 5 vines x 4 block x 3 treatments). A schema of the experimental design is reported in Figure 28. The three treatments will be the following:

- Business as usual (BaU): the vineyard parcel will be managed according to the disease management strategy that each wine-company normally use in their commercial vineyards (which may vary depending on the company).
- Control: the vineyard parcel will be managed postponing the sprayings until the appearance of the symptoms of the first mildew attacks and then it will follow the commercial protocol for disease management. This treatment will be used mainly for calibration/training and fine-tuning of the model.
- VITIGEOSS management: the vineyard parcel will be managed taking advantage of the information provided by the VITIGEOSS disease risk management model. These treatments will be used for model validation/fine-tuning purposes.

The BaU and the Control treatment will be applied for three consecutive vegetative seasons, whereas the VITIGEOSS management treatment will be applied in the second and third vegetative seasons (first year of the project will be dedicated to collect data for model calibration). The Syrah plot will be used only for model validation/fine-tuning purposes and will include only the BaU and VITIGEOSS management treatments applied in the second and third vegetative seasons.

Figure 28: Schema of experimental design used for the disease symptom assessment in the field. Each circle represents one vine.

2.2.3 Measurements

2.2.3.1 Disease symptom monitoring

The occurrence of disease symptoms caused by downy mildew and powdery mildew will be monitored throughout the vegetative seasons. Symptom assessment will be done following the international code supported by the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization [14]. Following this code, the following parameters will be monitored:

- disease incidence (calculated as the number of leaves/grapes with symptoms divided by the total number of observed leaves/grapes).
- disease severity (expressed as a percentage of the leaf blade area showing symptoms)

To assess these parameters, three-five randomly selected leaves per vine will be visually observed. After stage I (open flower), three-five randomly bunches per vine will be visually observed. To help the assessment of the disease severity parameter, the evaluators will be provided with the reference images suggested by the OEPP/EPPO [14]. A re-elaborated version of some these reference example images is reported in Figure 29. Measurement frequency will vary from biweekly to weekly depending on the risk of occurrence of disease attacks (rainfall, air temperature).

Figure 29: Reference images for disease severity assessment. Three levels of disease severity (5%, 50% and 90%) are reported (re-elaborated from OEPP/EPPO [14]).

2.2.3.2 Phytosanitary treatments monitoring

The phytosanitary treatments applied for the three disease management strategies will be monitored by using two approaches. On one side, the end users will provide information of their field activities regarding these treatments: application dates, type of applied products, amount of applied phytosanitary product/s, amount of applied water, expected dose and area treated. On the other hand, the sprayers and tractor used for the application of these treatments will be monitored using a datalogging system connected to the cloud. The specifications of the datalogging solution are included in the “Annex A: Machinery datalogging requirements v1”.

2.3 Key crop indicators

The aim of this field activity will be to select parcels where collecting the data required to calibrate/train, fine-tuning and validate the key crop indicators model. With this aim several vineyard parcels will be chosen at the different locations and they will include as many cultivars as possible.

2.3.1 Selected parcels

The parcels that will be used for this objective will be located at a total of 8 sites (five in Italy, two in Portugal, and one in Spain).

2.3.1.1 Parcels at Mirabella Eclano (Mastroberardino)

At this experimental site, a total of 11 parcels will be used to collect data and satellite images required to calibrate/validate the key crop indicator model. These parcels have a size ranging between around 1.0 and 5.5 ha (for a total of 24 ha) and include a total of three white cultivars (Falanghina, Fiano, and Greco) and one red cultivar (Aglianico). The parcels at Mirabella Eclano selected for this part of the project are reported in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Selected parcels at Mirabella Eclano estate.

2.3.1.2 Parcels at Montefusco (Mastroberardino)

At this site, four parcels will be selected for these project activities. The parcels are all cultivated with the cultivar Greco and their size ranges between 0.6 and 4.0 ha. The selected parcels at Montefusco are shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31: Selected parcels at Montefusco estate.

2.3.1.3 Parcels at Montemarano (Mastroberardino)

At the Montemarano estate, two Aglianico parcels with a size of 3.0 and 4.5 ha will be used for collecting data needed to calibrate the key crop indicator models. These parcels are shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32: Selected parcels at Montemarano estate.

2.3.1.4 Parcels at Pietradefusi (Mastroberardino)

At this experimental site, one Aglianico parcel of a total size of 2.30 ha will be used for this part of the projects. This parcel was already described in this document in one of the sections dedicated to the phenology models (Figure 9).

2.3.1.5 Parcels at Santa Paolina (Mastroberardino)

At the Santa Paolina estate, two Greco parcels with a size of 0.7 and 4.0 ha will be used for collecting data needed to calibrate the key crop indicator models. These parcels are shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33: Selected parcels at Santa Paolina estate.

2.3.1.6 Parcels at Quinta do Ataíde (Symington)

At the experimental site of Quinta do Ataíde, a total of 71 parcels will be used to collect data and satellite images required to calibrate/validate the key crop indicator model (Figure 34). These parcels have a size ranging between around 0.089 ha and 2.502 ha (for a total of 82.663 ha) and include a total of 1 white cultivar (Rabigato) and 7 red cultivars (Touriga Nacional, Touriga Franca, Tinta Barroca, Tinta Roriz, Malvasia Preta, Tinto Cão and Mourisco).

Figure 34: Selected parcels at Quinta do Ataíde estate.

2.3.1.7 Parcels at Quinta do Bomfim (Symington)

At the experimental site of Quinta do Bomfim, a total of 88 parcels will be used to collect data and satellite images required to calibrate/validate the key crop indicator model (Figure 35). These parcels have a size ranging between 0.027 and 3.207 ha (for a total of 74.634 ha) and include a total of 6 red cultivars (Alicante Bouschet, Tinto Cão, Sousão, Tinta Barroca, Touriga Nacional and Touriga Franca).

Figure 35: Selected parcels at Quinta do Bomfim estate.

2.3.1.8 Parcels at Aranyó (Torres)

At the experimental site of Aranyó, a total of 8 parcels will be used to collect data and satellite images required to calibrate/validate the key crop indicator model (Figure 36). These parcels have a size ranging between 1.67 and 8.84 ha (for a total of 33 ha) and include a total of eight red cultivars (Alicante Bouschet, Cabernet-Sauvignon, Cariñena, Garnacha negra, Garró, Merlot, Syrah, and Tempranillo).

Figure 36: Selected parcels at Aranyó estate.

2.3.2 *Measurements*

In each selected parcel, total fruit yield will be measured at harvest. In addition, in the irrigated parcels, the total amount of water applied with irrigation will be measured.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The pilot plots designed and described in this document have the objective of providing all the parcels and field trials required to collect enough data to calibrate/train and validate the models included in VITIGEOSS. To assure the robustness of the model calibration and validation, the design aimed to include as many parcels and grape cultivars as possible. To achieve this goal a total of around 235 ha of vineyards located in nine locations will be involved in the projects and they will include a total of more than 180 parcels and 21 cultivars. For each of the models, specific experimental designs were defined for the collection of the data.

4. REFERENCES

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5. ANNEXES

An annex is included in another file called “Annex_A_Machinery_datalogging_requirements_v1.pdf” describing the requirements for the machinery datalogging system.

